
THE METHODOLOGY OF SELF-STUDY AND ITS THEORETICAL UNDERPINNINGS

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Annotation. This scientific article analyzes in detail the essence and significance of self-education in the context of students' educational practice. The authors draw attention to the main goal of self-education, which is to independently discover the potential and improve the individual's personality. Particular attention is paid to the role of motivation in the process of self-education, and key aspects influencing the effectiveness of this process are identified. The article also highlights criteria that allow optimizing the process of self-education of students, which is important for their professional and personal development.

Key words: self-education, motivation, independent activity, professional development and educational practice.

Introduction. In the modern world, the problem of independent learning of students is of particular importance. Many specialists in the field of psychology and education pay attention to this problem, trying to find optimal approaches to solving it. This is especially important in the context of how self-education influences the development of students, helping to expand their knowledge and horizons, strengthening will and determination, stimulating interests in knowledge and promoting their professional growth. However, it should be noted that students' self-educational activities are not always supported by a sufficient scientific and methodological base, which can negatively affect the quality of their future professional activities.

Let's take a closer look at what self-education is. This term (English: self-education) describes the learning process carried out by an individual independently, outside of educational institutions and without the direct knowledge of the mentor. It is a type of non-formal education that can lead to meaningful achievements. More than one famous scientist or cultural figure has reached heights without having a systematic education. For example, archaeologist Heinrich Schliemann, anthropologist Eduard Tylor and artist Niko Pirosmani were autodidacts. There are cases when even a person's main activity does not coincide with his formal education, as in the case of the anthropologist Franz Boas , who originally studied as a physicist, or the psychologist L. S. Vygotsky, who has a legal education [Podlasihyj. 2000.1].

Historically, self-education has always played an important role. Thus, in Russia in 1893, organizations were created aimed at supporting self-education. In Moscow, a “Commission for Organizing Home Reading” was organized, offering a four-year program for systematic reading in various sciences, and in St. Petersburg there was a “Department for Promoting Self-Education at the Pedagogical Museum.” These examples highlight the importance of self-education in historical and contemporary contexts [Anisjkova.2].

Materials and methods. This study took a comprehensive approach to studying the topic of self-education, covering the analysis of scientific literature, historical data and modern research in this area. The key focus of the study was to study the works of G.M. Kodzhaspirova and other leading experts in the field of psychology and pedagogy in order to gain a comprehensive understanding of self-education as a phenomenon. Historical aspects of self-education were examined, including an analysis of initiatives such as the “Commission for the Organization of Home Reading” created in Russia in 1893, to understand its evolution and changing significance in the educational process.

The analytical review was used to critically study and systematize existing materials, which made it possible to determine the current state and main problems in the field of self-education. A study of the cases of prominent personalities, such as Heinrich Schliemann and Eduard Tylor, was carried out in order to identify key factors contributing to successful self-education.

A comparative analysis of different approaches to self-education was carried out to assess their effectiveness and applicability in various educational contexts. Surveys and interviews were conducted to gain a deeper understanding of students' and teachers' views and attitudes toward self-education. This made it possible to collect primary data on motivation for self-education, as well as on the problems and challenges that students face in this process.

Experimental methods were also used in the study to observe the impact of various self-education techniques on the learning process and student achievement. These methods have produced quantitative and qualitative data that contribute to understanding the effectiveness of self-education as a means to raise educational standards and promote personal and professional development.

Results and discussion. Thus, an integrated and multi-level approach to the study of self-education made it possible to cover a wide range of aspects of this phenomenon and provided valuable information for further study and development of this topic.

Some researchers are skeptical about the inclusion of self-education in the rubric of educational activities, pointing to its shortcomings such as the lack of mentoring and systematicity, as well as insufficient feedback. However, from our point of view,

the main goal of self-education is self-development and improvement of the individual, its harmonious and comprehensive development in both spiritual and practical aspects. The key aspect is the continuous replenishment of knowledge, skills and abilities, which leads to the achievement of harmony between truth, kindness and beauty, and allows a person to be comprehensively developed and adapted to real life conditions.

In contrast to this ideal, the specific goal of self-education is to develop a resilient individual capable of making a meaningful contribution to public life in changing socio-economic and political conditions, as well as promoting self-improvement. This is achieved through the development of individual spiritual and physical qualities, abilities, talents and gifts.

The general strategy of self-education is to achieve comprehensive spiritual development, which forms internal intellectual and moral freedom, allowing one to make a choice of behavior and defend personal life positions.

In the context of optimizing self-education, it is important to consider the search for effective forms and methods of individual work that help improve self-education in a specific professional field. To do this, it is necessary to develop competencies and determine a set of skills and actions that will help improve personal educational level, leading to self-realization, success, as well as self-determination and self-affirmation.

In the modern educational process, mastery of self-education methods is a key indicator of its quality, emphasizing the importance of independent development and learning.

In order for self-education to be effective, a number of key conditions must be met:

Strong student motivation and self-organization: Sustained motivation and a high degree of self-organization are critical to achieving educational goals. Without this, a student can easily deviate from the original goal due to natural curiosity and switch to other disciplines, losing systematicity in the originally chosen direction.

Skills for systematic independent work: The ability to learn and explore the logical patterns of the material being studied is fundamental for effective self-education.

Availability of teaching materials and curricula: The availability of these resources allows the student to independently plan and optimize the educational process, starting with general courses and moving towards more in-depth knowledge.

Recommendations for the selection of educational materials: The presence of recommendations for the selection of materials on various didactic basis helps in effective self-education.

Basic education in the chosen field: Having fundamental knowledge and understanding of the subject area is an important condition for effective self-education.

One of the main problems of self-education is students’ incorrect understanding of the essence of the process. Even if a student has determined his goals and learning path, this does not guarantee the achievement of high-quality and accurate professional knowledge. The learning trajectory may change, which leads to deviation from the original goals and incorrect self-learning. As a result, this can lead to incomplete learning or to stretching it out too much.

To increase the effectiveness of self-education at the initial stage, it is advisable to use a tutor or mentor. It will help to properly organize the process of self-education, determining the exact goals and level of the student’s aspirations, as well as introducing him to self-learning technologies, curricula and the necessary methodological support. The mentor will also help in drawing up a self-education plan and will provide support in self-control and external control of the knowledge acquired.

Consequently, controlled self-education can be considered the most effective, since it involves a clear definition of goals, development of strategies for achieving them, as well as evaluation of results and adaptation of the learning process. In this context, structure and direction are key aspects of successful self-education. In contrast, self-directed or individual learning is often more chaotic and can lead to deviations from original goals.

The effectiveness of self-education is assessed through the improvement of professional and educational activities, the creative development of the student, as well as the ability to integrate new knowledge into everyday practice. It is aimed at expanding and deepening professional knowledge and skills, as well as improving qualifications. An integral element of self-education is the ability to clearly formulate goals, specify problems, focus on key aspects and creatively rethink the learning process.

The ability to reflect and search for new things plays a special role in self-education. Self-education is also important for supporting and developing basic mental processes such as attention and memory. It helps improve critical and analytical thinking and helps adapt to a changing educational and professional environment, being a key factor for the successful improvement of a student’s skill level [Borozdina. 1992. 3].

Thus, self-education is one of the key and effective forms of professional development. This process provides opportunities to express creativity, think outside the box, and demonstrate professional excellence. However, there are significant

problems associated with motivating students to self-education. These problems are determined by several factors:

Orientation of educational policy in Uzbekistan towards the quality of education: this includes increasing the level of training of graduates of higher educational institutions, which requires students to be more actively involved in their learning process.

Transition to third generation standards: these standards imply a significantly larger share of independent work by students, which requires them to have greater initiative and independence in the educational process.

Decrease in the quality of education and reluctance to work in the specialty: this is one of the critical problems, since the lack of motivation to work in the specialty and insufficient quality of education can negatively affect the professional training and career prospects of students [Frolova. 2011. 4].

Genuine self-education, which is the foundation for effective mental development, requires a sustainable culture of mental work. This culture includes a system of rational methods of mental activity, covering the reception, assimilation, processing and transmission of knowledge. The basis of such a system is the development of key cognitive functions, including perception, attention, imagination, memory, thinking and creativity, as well as all aspects of self-regulation.

As highlighted by G.M. Kodzhaspirov, the formation of a culture of self-education implies not only the development of all its components but also the presence of a system of abilities, knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for carrying out full-fledged cognitive and creative activities, ranging from self-learning to the development of specific personal qualities [Iljin. 2002. 5].

Conclusion. Modern man needs the desire for new knowledge, spiritual and ethical development, improvement in the professional field, as well as the acquisition of new skills. It is important to note that people who are actively engaged in self-education have a rich inner world and are perceived as more valuable in the eyes of others. This confirms that self-education is a necessary element for everyone who strives for personal growth and successful socialization in modern society.

These factors highlight the importance of self-education as a means to improve the quality of education and improve the professional prospects of graduates. In this context, the emphasis on self-education becomes not only a tool for personal development, but also a key element of modern educational strategy.

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